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To: 'Mattan Schlomi' <mattanschlomi@aol.com>
Subject: Uploaded your Article in Online AG-MRW-19-0545
Date: Wed, Dec 4, 2019 4:05 pm

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Regards,

Catherine Nichols

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From: Mattan Schlomi <mattanschlomi@aol.com>
Sent: Tuesday, December 3, 2019 5:35 PM
To: agri@biomedgrid-nl.net
Subject: Re: Acceptance for Publication: AG-MRW-19-0545

Hello,

It is acceptable! You may upload.

Dr. Mattan Schlomi

mattanschlomi@aol.com